

Surrenderism: A Philosophy for Easy Life¹

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In Kavre district, Kalpana's sister-in-law (*bhauju*) took her own life. Kalpana, because of melancholic personality, tormented herself by this accident for months just because she could not spend enough time with her dead relative or counsel her brother to detect the cues of suicide and hence take measures to avert it. She was forgetting the fact that she was a busy married working woman herself with her own family to take care of and would meet maternal relatives just thrice or four times a year evanescently. She was distressed for a long time and then further fell into depression. How should she have reacted to the premature expiry of a relative? The answer lies in surrenderism, a new philosophy of life proposed here.

Life is a thread of events made up of numerous changes in physique, psyche, self, and the world around spanning a duration between life and death. The saying goes that the only constant is change. Still, we panic about denying, resisting, or refusing the changes that occur around us rather than surmounting them. How would our life be if we accepted every vicissitude in life pretty easily? Surrenderism is the doctrine that we should surrender to changes in life without resistance and move on. Simply put, we surrender to life. Adapting to context asap is a great idea to smoothen our daily living. Resistance to change results in negative stress and degraded quality of life (QoL). Why choose fuss if life can be plastered by joyous peace! Mental distress may result from the denial of what has happened to us in life.

Life consists of both controllable and uncontrollable aspects. There are many constraints in life and they are overpowering. People can exercise a degree of freedom in any number or intensity of constraints. For instance, litterateurs could not change the political system, nor write against the King during Panchayat era. Still, they could WRITE on social or economic issues. Constraints can be economical, environmental, moral, physical, or else. We have command over controllable aspects of life. We cannot choose the size of an ear for us but can opt for the kind of ornament we put on it. We can choose the career that satisfies us rather than garner wealth devoid of fulfillment. We can select a compatible and understanding partner for life, business or combined study. For controllable aspects, we can evaluate, monitor, learn, plan, and act carefully to get desired results. Nonetheless, the surety of results is not in our hands. There are other uncontrollable aspects of life. We have to accept them sooner or later, resisting or not, nagging or not. Better we accept them peacefully soon and adapt to new circumstances. Native Kathmanduites might be complaining that their city is

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dirtied by immigrants. As a person, they can do nothing to clean it wholly (however much they are eco-friendly in behavior). So, they can live life better if they accept the fact about Kathmandu's pollution sooner rather than later and start adaptational endeavors. At least, they can mitigate their psychological perturbation and have more mental health.

Surrenderism does not mean we become passive actors or reactive organisms. We have to be proactive creatures who have to envisage a better future for themselves and others. We also have to look back at our past actions, behaviors, and experiences and learn from them to deliberate our tomorrow and act wisely. "Be an active actor as well as an active witness of results, but passive aspirant" should be our mantra. We aspire less about results because after we act on our part, results come out in their own right. Miss Nepal 2018 Shrinkhala Khatiwada said that she did not regret not winning Miss World because she tried her best and the result was not in her hand. The Gita puts it, "Do duties, care not about outcomes". Surrenderists also do not deny challenges. Challenges also might be stressful but if they are distress-inducing, surrenderists suggest people to drop or lessen those challenges. "Cut your coat according to the size of the cloth." Psychologists have found that stress, to a degree, can enhance people's performance. They also say that goals are more motivating if they are specific, attainable, and challenging.

To deal with the uncertainty of outcomes, we should cultivate "emotional insurance" and get ready for negative consequences as well as for positive consequences. Emotional insurance is the concept that people should get ready to face the unexpected. It helps to face any negatives that may happen in life. It is not pessimism. It is living life happily but separating space for possible failure or trauma in life. Scientists are constantly searching for the power to predict handsomely. Even though they can predict somewhat now, their predictive power is a drop in the ocean. They can foretell in a very minutely specific situation currently. Uncertainty of results (or uncertainty in life all in all) is nerve-wracking but it is also a beautiful thing to cherish. As the renowned lead character in the picture 'Forrest Gump' says, "... Life was like a box of chocolates. You never know what you are gonna get." Uncertainty can be sweet concerning the surprises it brings forth. We can use the tool of mindfulness to tell apart uncontrollable from controllable aspects of life. We should try to affect controllable elements and surrender to uncontrollable factors or outcomes. In the Hindu and Buddhist philosophy, many people accept outcomes with the principle of karma. Karma meant proportionate causality initially but people take it as fate these days. Moreover, the flaw with this principle is that people might have to bear the results of previous births which might not exist. People think that karma cannot be changed. Pundits preach by saying if we perform good deeds, we can reap good results after death or in the following birth. Present-day humans need an immediate philosophy.

We face many unexpected changes in life. Denial is a natural reaction in such a situation. Mindfulness can alleviate it. Mere awareness can be a nudge for actions in a certain direction. Mindfully, we should observe our context. We also should be evaluative about how we are performing our duties. We have to learn from the past, act wisely in the present, and plan for a good future. Proactivity is a key component of surrenderism. People just cannot react; they should take the initiative to shape the future in the desired direction. They cannot lament how the outcome turns out. They just accept it and move on; this is the rule in surrenderism.

Had Kalpana surrendered to life changes quickly, she would have been safe from the emotional and mental turmoil that marred her life for so long. One day, she recovered but her phase of mental health problems had incurred much loss that could have been avoided by the philosophy of surrenderism.

SURRENDERISM

Surrender to life

Learn from past

Plan for future

Do not resent on

the uncontrollable

**Accept
changes in
life without
resistance**

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